

Representation of Eco-feminism in Matrilineal Meghalaya Community in Northeast India; Janice Pariat's *We Come from Mist:* *writings from Meghalaya*

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Abstract: *Meghalaya is a matrilineal society. Matrilineal culture has close ties to ecology and feminism. The most popular perception of ecofeminism is the rise of women against the patriarchal dominance on both nature and the women. The objective of the present study is to analyse the selected works from the book, We Come from Mist, writings from Meghalaya by Janice Pariat, to investigate the notion of representation of ecofeminism in the Meghalayan matrilineal community in Northeast India. The present study analyses the selected narratives from the aforementioned book along with the theories related to ecofeminism. The selected works of the book are, 'Forget-Me-Not' by Satrupa Paul, 'The Women in Between' by Saweini Laloo, 'The Wheel and the Reel' by Daiarisa Rum-nong and 'Three-night Rain' by Antara Roy Oruganti. The research question pursues the question of how the representation of ecofeminism emerges in the matrilineal Meghalayan community in Northeast India.*

Keywords: *Eco-feminism, Ecology, Feminism, Meghalaya, Narratives.*

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Eco-feminists in India were having a resilient connection with nature. As Suman and Poornananda (2016) mention that the tribes of Meghalaya, including Khasi, Jaintia, and Garo, follow the matrilineal societal structure and maintain a close relationship with nature (17). According to Palliyalil & Mukherjee (2020) the concept of matrilineality has been in existence for almost 2000 years, which aims to uphold a woman's freedom and preserve her wealth in Meghalaya. Eco-feminism is a social movement and also an ecological ideology that focuses its attention on the notion that historically, women are more concerned about environmental issues than men (Birkeland 45).

1.2 Problem Statement

Meghalaya is a matrilineal society where the women have deep ecological connections with the nature. Rao (2012) mentions the ways in which marriage, family, religion and food cultures of the tribes of Meghalaya integrated the nature into their daily lives. Also, they regard nature as their mother who protects them from harm (6). Matrilineal culture supports the environmental protection and also, provides the equal importance to the women and the nature. The nature also plays a significant role in the lives of the women. Simultaneously, these women take extreme measures to preserve the nature. As a result, the Meghalayan women community came forefront with preserving the nature. The aforementioned idea facilitated Eco-feminism.

Prasad & Mina (2015) mentions that the most popular perception of ecofeminism is the rise of women against the patriarchal dominance on both nature and the women. Therefore, Ecofeminists believed that women are the protectors of nature (8). Shiva (1988) states that degradation of women and nature is due to the emergence of the new world order and that is based on the development, modernization and advancement in science and technology. This patriarchal concept of the modern development caused the exploitation of nature. The women are the saviours of nature (45) The patriarchal society that which represents the modern industrialized

society degraded the women and nature (53).

The selected book for the present research is the book, *we come from Mist, the writings of Meghalaya* (2023) encompassed prose, fiction, non-fiction and poetry which were produced by Meghalayan women community in Northeast India while focusing on a variety of themes including, fraternal bond, woman as social worker, the healing power of nature on women, folk wisdom and parenting. Janice Pariat is the author who is from hillside of Meghalaya.

1.3 The objective of the research study

The objective of the present research study is to analyze the selected works from the book, *we come from Mist; Writings from Meghalaya* by Janice Pariat in order to investigate the notion of representation of ecofeminism in Matrilineal Meghalayan community in Northeast India.

1.4 Research Question

How does representation of ecofeminism emerge in matrilineal Meghalayan community in Northeast India that which depict in the selected narratives of the book, *we come from Mist; Writings from Meghalaya* by Janice Pariat?

2. Methodology

2.1 Scope of the study

Primarily, the present research study analyses the selected narratives of the book, *we come from Mist; Writings from Meghalaya* by Janice Pariat. Along with the above, the theories related to the fields of Ecology and its impact on women, Eco-feminism, Eco Feminism in India, and Matrilineal Culture in Meghalaya have been extensively referred.

The selected narratives of the book, *we come from Mist; Writings from Meghalaya* by Janice Pariat are,

Forget-Me-Not by Satrupa Paul (14)

The Women in Between by Saweini Laloo (79)

The Wheel and the Reel by Daiarisa Rumnong (98)

Three-night Rain by Antara Roy Oruganti (220)

2.2 Research Design

The methodology of the present research study uses a qualitative research design where the selected narratives of the book, *we come from Mist; Writings from Meghalaya* by Janice Pariat is analyzed using 'Textual analysis.'

The narratives have been analyzed using the theories which have been created after referring the research articles of research scholars in the field of Eco-feminism. The selected narratives have been analysed using the following themes,

1. The connection in between oppression of women and the oppression of nature. When women protested on ecological destruction, they discovered the connections between patriarchal domination and violence against women.
2. Ecofeminism recognizes the notion that historically, women are more concerned on environmental issues than men. Therefore, women are closer to nature than men.

3. Results and Discussion

1. The connection in between oppression of women and the oppression of nature. When women protested on ecological destruction, they discovered the connections in between patriarchal domination and violence against women.

In the poem, 'The Women in Between' by Saweini Laloo discusses a very important point in relation to the fragility of women at the patriarchal hands of men. The metaphor of 'women in between' signifies that the everyday dilemma

that which was faced by the women community because of men. This women's oppression is similar to the oppression of nature. The poet brings out many instances to showcase that women's oppression or the nature's oppression through her poetic verses. In this poem, the portrayal of 'Meira Paibi' is unique because these women fought against the patriarchal dominance and the violence that has been happened against the women.

Oinam & Thoidingjam (2020) state that 'The Meira Paibi' is a women community who lived in Manipur while carrying fire torch as a weapon, they expressed their anger on the social injustice. Sometimes, all the women community in Manipur transformed themselves into 'Meira Paibi' when the difficult circumstances arose. The inception of this community of 'Meira Paibi' was formed at the pre- and post-independence period of India. Through the action of silent marching, they protest for the violation of human rights and the women rights (20). When these women fight against the social oppression of the women community, for an eco-feminist which connotes the idea that these women struggle against saving the nature. Laloo (2023) echoed the voice of a 'Meira Paibi' where she believed she should raise her voice against the violation of the women rights. The aforementioned idea is reflected as follows,

“Just like my sister
Manorama
Who remained true and pure
And refused to lick paws of those beasts
Even as they tore her body to shreds
On her soil
In the dead of night.” (Laloo 24-30)

In the poem, 'The Wheel and the Reel' (98) which is written by Daiarisa Rumnong discusses about the cultural conflict in between the women community. The modern woman was oppressed by the cultural circumstances. As a tradition of the Meghalayan women community, they stitch and sew the clothes. The poetess tries her level best of being a talented tailor as of her grandmother. Yet, 'stitching' seems not to be her cup of tea. The poetess states that she is supposed to learn her grandmother's passion because she is being the next line to take over her grandmother's passion that matters the maternal family kinship.

“I sit before my grandmother's sewing machine
Calculating thread, needle, wheel.
My feet are alien to the rhythm of the pedal.
I should learn” (Rumnong 1-4)

The poetess is not familiar with stitching. Her action of sewing is compared to her survival in the Meghalayan community. She puts countless efforts to stitch her cloth in her own way, on the contrary, she feels that she is not successful in her stitching. It seemed to be that the maternal family lineage is yielded to oppress the women who lived in the contemporary Meghalaya. The living example is provided by the poetess through commemorating her maternal family lineage and continued with stitching, though her “hands panting pale behind them.” When the woman was oppressed, the emphasis is that the nature has been oppressed. Her passion was overshadowed by the dominant maternal lineage. In that manner, the present work of Janice Pariat challenged the conventional ecofeminist idea of the patriarchal dominance over the nature through violating the women community. On the contrary, it was clear that the woman can be oppressed not only due to the patriar-

chal circumstances yet the inclusion of other circumstances like maternal family lineage.

In her fictional prose, 'Three-night Rain' (220) by Antara Roy Oruganti discusses about the reunion of two school best friends after so many years. They are Pearl and Debu. Pearl is a widow who lost her husband and having spent such a lonely life without much exposing to the outside world. On the other hand, Debu is worried over the loss of his mother. The two individuals seemed to be insecure about their personal histories to be revealed because digging of the past brings them frustration which caused them so much pain. However, the nature becomes an instant comfort where they were able to share their personal stories and spoke their hearts out. The two friends were wondering whether how did they share their unforgettable past and realized that it was because of rain that they were able to open up their bottled up feelings.

"I suppose we like to share our stories, happy or sad, whenever it rains this way." Why do you think that happens?

It could be the rain, that rhythmic, drumming music. That kind of music makes you want to open up your heart.'

'So, is it a good idea to open up one's heart?'

'It always is,' he said, leaning closer and looking her straight in the eye. It looks like you have not opened up your heart at all, not for ages.' 'This is the first time I ever spoke about it to anyone.' (231)

Surprisingly, it was not only the woman who was oppressed because of certain circumstances in their lives as Pearl, the man too gets oppressed. Debu as a man who get oppressed, was able to identify that he was enchanted by the nature that which makes him to open up his heart to Pearl. Debu has become a soft person to appreciate the nature. Not only the woman, the man also fascinated by the nature. In the present contemporary collection, the traditional idea of patriarchal dominance over ecology and the feminism has been challenged because the man loves the nature as the woman does. Another significant instance can be drawn as follows, Debu has written a letter to Pearl where he has mentioned as following,

"And dear Pearl, through the hours that I sat here, waiting for you, I made friends with all your plants and trees, and of course, Romila brews the best tea (236)."

2. Ecofeminism recognizes the notion that historically, women are more concerned on environmental issues than men. Therefore, women are closer to nature than men.

In her fictional prose, 'Forget-Me-Not' by Satrupa Paul mentioned the ways in which both man and the woman were fascinated by the nature. The story showcases the two dimensions; the ways in which Shyama was cared by Raju Dada and the ways in which Shyama cared for her little brother. Shyama loves 'Forget-Me-Not' flower and gives those flowers to her brother because she realizes that her brother loves them.

"And how much you loved those blue flowers too! Your eyes shone bright when I brought you a bunch every day after school and waved it in front of you, just out of your reach. You always tried to reach your arms up and touch them (24)"

Unexpectedly, her brother died. His loss was unbearable to Shyama. The nature can both strengthen and influence the human emotions unapologetically. Shyama was moved away from her brother's action of keeping the blue flower in

his fist. Simultaneously, he felt the smell of her brother from the same petals. On the other hand, Raju dada is a man who softens himself because of the nature and used the very same nature to console Shyama. In that way, it seems that not only the woman but the man is also softened by the nature.

“Your brother may not be there with you anymore, in your house or your life. But he’ll always be there in you, in your heart and your mind. He’ll live on in your memory forever and you’ll never forget him.’ Just like a Forget-Me-Not.” (30)

In the fictional prose, ‘Three-night Rain’ by Antara Roy Oruganti mediates the human emotions with the nature through using folk wisdom. Here, Oruganti uses the natural element of ‘rain.’ Pearl believes that this rain would stop because she expects the nature to bring the positivity to her. Yet, the servant with her folk wisdom states that the rain would not stop. And that brings to the note that the nature has a deep connection with the folk wisdom of the women. Simultaneously, that resulted the fact that the woman is closer to the nature.

“Pearl was waiting for her friend. She predicts that the rain would stop, and her friend would come. But Romila, her servant has mentioned that ‘No khun, this is not that kind of rain.’” (227)

The writer used literary techniques like, similes while relating to the nature. The following is one such example where the movement of the nature is closely related with the body movement of the woman. The body movement of the servant, Romila has been compared to a leaf which is moved in the wind and rain. This reflection of Pearl is her innate behaviour of appreciating the nature. Because Pearl is being closer to the nature, she was able to appreciate a human through relating to the nature. This showcases the ways in which the woman gets closer to the nature.

“Pearl watched with a smile as Romila hurried away towards the kitchen, her nimble body coursing ahead like a slender, long leaf nudged by the wind and rain.” (236)

Conclusion

The impact of nature on different layers of women was depicted. La-loo depicts the life of ‘Meira Paibi’ community in Manipur who raised their voice against the patriarchal dominance and the violence of the human rights. Each woman suffered the dark chapters of the life due to inhuman men. In the perspective of the eco-feminists, the life of women is compared to the nature and that nature is victimized by the patriarchy. On the contrary, Oruganti explored a controversial idea of eco-feminism. It was not only the woman, but the man, ‘Debu’ was also sad in his entire life due to the loss of his mother and got healed at the presence of the nature. Therefore, it was not only the woman but the man also got healed by the nature. Paul mentioned that it was not only ‘Shyama’ but also ‘Raja Dada’ was softened by the nature because he reminded Shyama that your brother would live in your memory as this flower, ‘Forget-Me-Not.’ In addition to the above mentioned argument, Rumnong mentions that her action of sewing is compared to her survival in the Meghalayan community. She put countless efforts to stitch her cloth in her own way, on the contrary, she felt that she was not successful in her stitching. She was oppressed because her passion was shadowed in her family lineage. Therefore, the circumstances like family lineage of the maternal community also impacted on the oppression of the woman. It seemed that the so called traditional eco-feminism is no longer available in India including the Meghalayan community. Eventually, the nature is owned by human without consider-

ing their gender because the oppression is universal which you cannot categorize into female oppression and that which is similar to the oppression of the nature. Being closer to the nature heal both man and the woman.

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